

Antimicrobial Activity of *Acalypha indica* (Bugos) Against Test Microorganism: Basis for the Formulation of A Broad- Spectrum Sanitizing Spray and Liquid Soap

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Abstract. In today's time, more pathogens are becoming resistant to traditional antibiotics, and their environmental impact, finding natural, fair products and alternatives has become essential. This study evaluated the potential of *Acalypha indica* (Bugos) as a source of antimicrobial agents for formulating broad-spectrum sanitizing spray and liquid soap suitable for household use. The study employed experimental research involving ethanol extraction of bioactive compounds from *A. indica* plant using percolation. The extract was quantitatively evaluated through yield determination and Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC). Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC), Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC), and zone of inhibition assays were conducted to assess its antimicrobial efficacy against selected Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, as well as fungi. The ethanol extract yielded 43.40%. MIC values as low as 15.6 µg/mL were observed, especially against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Disk diffusion test produced inhibition effect on Gram-positive, Gram-negative bacteria, and fungi. However, tests conducted to determine the strength of the developed sanitizing spray and liquid soap were found to be low compared to commercial disinfectants, and thus, it could only be used as a household product. Such a result highlights the possibility of *Acalypha indica* being used as a natural disinfectant in home sanitation practices because of its antimicrobial properties. Additional studies must be conducted with separation and purification of active components, consistency in the concentration of preparations, and the long-term conditions of safety and stability of products in a broader application.

Keywords: Diffusion, ethanolic extract, inhibition, minimum bactericidal concentrations, minimum inhibitory concentrations

Background of the Study

Acalypha indica (Bugos) is a medicinal plant known for its long-standing ethnomedicinal use and reported presence of bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, and saponins, which exhibit antimicrobial properties (Cowan, 1999; Pharmaceutical Research Journal, 2021). These findings make *A. indica* a promising candidate for plant-based solutions against microbial pathogens. Despite the abundance of research on medicinal plants, studies focusing on *A. indica*—especially its activity against multidrug-resistant organisms like *P. aeruginosa* and *E. coli*—remain limited. Most prior research was conducted in vitro, lacking follow-through into practical applications like sanitizing products (Arulraj et al., 2017).

This study responds to the gap by investigating *A. indica*'s antimicrobial potential and using it as a basis for formulating broad-spectrum sanitizing spray and liquid soap. Plant-derived sanitizers offer advantages such as biodegradability, environmental safety, and effectiveness without adverse skin reactions (Gupta et al., 2013). Furthermore, due to increasing concerns over synthetic sanitizers' health and ecological impacts, natural alternatives are gaining attention (Azwanida, 2015).

There is still a lack of comprehensive evidence regarding *A. indica*'s effectiveness in real-world antimicrobial applications (Chopra & Roberts, 2001; Cushnie & Lamb, 2011). Therefore, developing practical hygiene solutions using this plant, particularly in healthcare and household settings, is both timely and necessary. This study aims to bridge that gap by evaluating the plant's efficacy and translating the results into accessible, eco-friendly, and affordable sanitation products, particularly useful in resource-limited communities.

Statement of the Objectives

This research study aimed to determine the antimicrobial potential of the different crude extracts of *Acalypha indica* (Bugos) and its formulated broad-spectrum sanitizing spray and liquid soap. This was conducted from February 2025 until May 2025.

Specifically, it answered the following problems:

1. What is the percent yield of the crude extract of *A. indica* (Bugos) using ethanol as solvent?
2. What are the Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentrations (MBC) of the crude extract of *A. indica* (Bugos) that can inhibit the selected pathogens: *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *B. subtilis*, *C. albicans*, *E. coli*, & *E. faecalis*?
3. What are the antimicrobial potentials of the formulated broad-spectrum sanitizing spray and liquid soap of *A. indica* (Bugos) that can inhibit the selected pathogens?

II. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized an experimental research method to determine the efficacy of *Acalypha indica* (Bugos) against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Escherichia coli*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *Candida albicans*. In this study, ethanolic crude extract of *Acalypha indica* was prepared and tested for its potential antimicrobial properties.

Study Site and Sample Collection

The study was conducted at Saint Mary's University, located in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines. The *A. indica* (Bugos) specimens, which typically grow in moist and shaded, were used in this study and were sourced from the open fields of Solano, Nueva Vizcaya. Though it grows in roadsides and wall crevices, the location is chosen strategically to minimize the chances of having the plant specimens picked from an area with industrial pollutants in the air because they will influence the phytochemical properties of the intended plant species. The extraction and carry-out of antimicrobial assays were in the Research Laboratory of Saint Mary's University, which possesses adequate equipment for microbial analysis.

Data Gathering Procedure

Preparation of Plant Sample

The collected *A. indica* samples were washed in distilled water in order to remove any adherent foreign particles and then dried naturally at room temperature. The samples were blended into a fine powder using an electric grinder upon a sufficient degree of drying that would end to additional moisture in the samples. The powdered plant material was kept in amber-white light, tightly capped (sealed) jars, or other airtight containers at room temperature until extraction.

Crude Extraction of Plant Material

Percolation was used for extracting bioactive compounds from *A. indica*, preserving phytochemicals and preventing the loss of heat-sensitive compounds. One hundred grams of dried, powdered plant material was soaked in 500 ml of 95% ethanol at 25°C for 24 hours, with intermittent shaking after 6 hours at 120 rpm to enhance extraction. To avoid photodegradation, the mixture was sealed and stored in a dark, temperature-controlled space (Kumar et al., 2023). As a traditional and effective method, percolation preserved thermostability and therapeutic value (Harborne, 1998; Pandey et al., 2014). The extract was filtered twice for clarity and concentrated using rotary evaporation at 40°C under reduced pressure, avoiding heat damage. The viscous crude extract was stored at 4°C in sterile vials for stability. This extract was then used for antimicrobial studies and formulation of broad-spectrum sanitizing spray and liquid soap.

Yield of Crude Extract

The yield of *A. indica* (Bugos) crude extract using ethanol was crucial in determining its antimicrobial activity against *S. aureus*, *P. aeruginosa*, *B. subtilis*, *C. albicans*, *E. coli*, and *E. faecalis*. The type of solvent influenced the type and amount of secondary metabolites extracted, which impacted the antimicrobial potential (Eloff, 1998; Tiwari et al., 2011). Ethanol, a polar solvent, effectively extracted phenolic compounds like flavonoids and tannins with antimicrobial properties (Cowan, 1999; Cushnie & Lamb, 2011). Similar findings from other plants like *Azadirachta indica* and *Moringa oleifera* supported ethanol's efficiency in yielding antimicrobial secondary metabolites (Siddiqui et al., 2015; Rahman et al., 2009; Iqbal et al., 2013). Less polar solvents like ethyl acetate also extracted bioactives, but ethanol remained superior for broader secondary metabolite yield (Tiwari et al., 2011; Handa et al., 2008).

Previous studies emphasized optimizing extraction to increase yield and efficacy, as in *Acalypha wilkesiana* and *Acalypha torta*, where extract properties depended on solvent used (Ndhlala et al., 2013; Olowokudejo et al., 2008). This study aimed to determine the percent yield of *A. indica* extracts using different solvents to find the most efficient for extracting antimicrobial compounds and for use in broad-spectrum sanitizing formulations.

Determination of Percent Yield of the A. indica Crude Extract

The percent yield determination was an important parameter to assess the extent of extraction of the bioactive compounds from *A. indica*. It measured the number of crude extracts extracted and the possibility of recovery of the secondary metabolites that are of economic importance, like alkaloids, flavonoids, and saponins. As for antimicrobial metabolites, they were commonly extracted with the help of solvents such as ethanol as they can solubilize a large range of polar and non-polar compounds (Pharmaceutical Research Journal, 2021; Gupta et al., 2013).

Ethanol was found to be useful for extracting bioactive compounds from medicinal plants while increasing the output of antimicrobial components. According to Ahmad et al. (1998), the maximization of secondary metabolite extraction and, therefore, antimicrobial potency of the extract was dependent on the polarity of a solvent. In this research, the percent yield of ethanol extraction of *A. indica* was determined to promote the easiest way of isolating bioactive compounds. These outcomes were applied to the formulation of antimicrobial products, such as sanitizing spray and liquid soap, and helped develop plant lead alternatives for chemical disinfectant products. The percent yield for each of the extract was determined using the formula:

$$LD_{50} = X_0 + (d \times \sum k) / n$$

Determination of Rf Values of Detected Secondary Metabolites of A. indica Crude Extract

Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was used to separate and identify secondary metabolites in the plant extract. Rf values were recorded to confirm the presence of certain phytochemicals based on their migration patterns. The Rf value (retention factor), defined as the distance that a compound traveled relative to the solvent front, was used to determine and compare compounds with regard to polarity and molecular weight (Cushnie & Lamb, 2011).

In this study, the bioactive compounds in *A. indica*, which are accountable for their antimicrobial function, were isolated on the basis of their Rf values using TLC. This characterization gave an understanding of the metabolites that gave this plant its broad-spectrum antimicrobial action, which is consistent with the objective of the study for formulating an effective sanitizing product.

Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) – Broth Microdilution Method

The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) for *A. indica* extract was carried out using the broth microdilution method for five replicates of each of the microorganisms. Serial dilutions of the *A. indica* extract were prepared and mixed with the suspensions of microbes in the 96-well plate to deliver robust and reproducible results. The replicative design eliminated random errors and maintained that differences in microbial increases came as a result of extract efficacy and not laboratory errors.

Subculturing test microorganisms prepared fresh culture media onto nutrient agar plates, and they were incubated at 37°C for 18–24 hours. The obtained colonies were transferred into the sterile saline solution, and the suspension was standardized to the 0.5 McFarland grade to provide equal microbial charges.

Stock solutions of *A. indica* crude extract were prepared in a solvent of choice, such as DMSO or ethanol, which allowed the solubilization with little stimulation to microorganisms. The extract was 2-times serially diluted in Mueller-Hinton broth for bacteria and Sabouraud Dextrose broth for fungi. In every well, 50 µL of broth was utilized. 50 µL extract was added, and 50 µL from the mixture was transferred to the next well until concentration levels started from 2,000 µg/mL down to 3.90 µg/mL. Later on, 50 µL of the microbial suspension was added to each well. The last volume per well was 100 µL, and microbial dilution was made, too. Positive control wells – contain known antibiotics, while negative controls – contain broth with no microorganisms or extract.

The microtiter plates were sealed to avoid contamination and evaporation and incubated at 37°C temperature for 18-24 hours. On incubation, the wells were observed for turbidity. For the given MIC, the extract concentration at which there was no visible microbial growth was defined. High absorbance corresponded with microbial growth and low inhibition.

Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) Determination

The Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) test was carried out after the performance of the MIC assay in a five-replicate format that aimed to guarantee a result reproducibility and accuracy. After detecting the MIC, only wells that had no visible turbidity were organized for sampling via sterile loops or swabs to find out if viable microorganisms were present in them. From each of these wells, the broth was streaked in sterile agar plates. This step was done with care in order not to contaminate. Agar plates were incubated at 37°C for 18–24 hours in order to provide a possibility for the regrowth of surviving organisms.

Microbial colony formation was used once plates were incubated to check them. The lack of colonies meant that the extract killed the microorganisms effectively. The MBC was, therefore, taken as the lowest concentration of the extract where no colony growth was evident. The extract at such a concentration was considered bacteriostatic and not as bactericidal when colonies were present.

Formulation of Broad-Spectrum Sanitizing Spray

The antimicrobial properties of the *A. indica* extract were taken advantage of during the formulation of a broad-spectrum sanitizing spray. This was based on the bioactive compounds-tannins, flavonoids, and alkaloids which have been proven to demonstrate antimicrobial action (Cowan, 1999). The extraction method involved soaking 100g of dried *A. indica* leaves in 500 ml 95% ethanol for 24 hours at room temperature shaking every 6 hours for maximal extraction. The

ethanol was thereafter removed from the extract by filtration through Whatman No. 1 filter paper and concentration using a rotary evaporator to give a final volume of 0.4ml.

In the method of Almeida et al. (2022), the spray formulation was made by heating 300 mL of clean water to 60°C. To this, 300 mL (Machinery, etc) (60 %) of 70 % ethanol was added as the main solvent and the antimicrobial. After this, 5% of glycerin in the amount of 25 mL was added to avoid irritation of the skin and have moisturizing properties. In addition, 5 ml (1%) of essential oils like tea tree was added for fragrance and antimicrobial purposes. A health treatment product was then prepared with the *A. indica* extract at its minimum bactericidal concentration level (MBC) to maximize the product's antimicrobial activity.

After proper mixing for a couple of minutes to have a homogeneous mixture, the solution was transferred into sterilized spray bottles. The final formulation was left to settle at room temperature for 24 hours and subjected to the antimicrobial test. In order to provide safety as well as compatibility with the skin, the formulation's pH was adjusted to the pH range of the skin. Skin-safe, and natural broad-spectrum sanitizing spray product was the resulting product that served such a purpose.

Formulation of Liquid Soap

The liquid soap was formulated by combining surfactants, emulsifiers, thickeners, and *A. indica* ethanolic extract, which is the main plant-based antibacterial agent. This formulation was in line with the findings of Tiwari et al. (2011), who underlined increasing interest in the use of botanical extract for increasing antimicrobial activity with the use of less harsh chemicals. It was aimed at producing a soap that could protect against common pathogens like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Candida albicans*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Enterococcus faecalis*.

For the soap base, 300ml of water was heated to 60°C. Then, 150 g (30%) of Sodium Lauryl Ether Sulfate (SLES) was slowly added whilst mixing at 200 rpm to avoid foaming. In a bid to enhance the stability of foam and lessen harshness, 50 g (10%) was added of Cocamidopropyl Betaine. This was then followed by the addition of 10 g (2%) PEG-150 Distearate as an emulsifier. Pre-dispersed in 10 mL (5%) glycerin, the gum of Xanthan was added for thickening at 5 g (0.5%). Phenoxyethanol (0.5% or 5 mL) was added to serve as a preservative to increase the product's shelf life and safety. Also, 10 mL (1%) of lemon essential oil has been added for fragrance and additional antimicrobial action (Tiwari et al., 2019).

When the mixture became smooth and cooled down to room temperature, all ingredients were poured into the sterilized pump bottles. The final product was maintained at 25°C for 24 hours before carrying out antimicrobial effectiveness tests. This formulation blended natural extract with basic cleaning qualities, producing a formulation that is fit for home purposes and health settings.

Evaluation of Formulated Sanitizing Spray and Liquid Soap

The antimicrobial activity of the formulated antimicrobial solutions from the ethanol extract of *A. indica* was determined by a disc diffusion test as CLSI (2015). Pieces of filter paper (the diameter of which was 6 mm) were soaked with formulated *A. indica* antimicrobial products. Sterile forceps were used to put these discs on agar plates that had been inoculated with the test organisms. The plates were left for incubation at 37°C for 24 hours. The measurements of the diameter of the zones of inhibition around discs with the aid of a digital caliper determined tests for antimicrobial activity. The interpretation for the measured zones of inhibition was based on Guevarra's zone diameter interpretative standard (2005). The zone of inhibition diameter descriptions are inactive (< 10 mm), partially active (10- 13 mm), active (14-19 mm), and very active (> 19 mm).

The disc diffusion method was used to evaluate the formulated sanitizing spray and liquid soap's antimicrobial activity, and its effectiveness was measured by its zone of inhibition. This is a technique that primes the test formulation into wells or discs placed on agar plates uniformly inoculated with microbe suspensions. After incubation, the millimeters of the area around each well or disc are measured where microbial growth has been prevented. The zone of inhibition is the

clear area, and its diameter directly corresponds to the antimicrobial product's efficacy. A larger zone implies a stronger bioactivity of the active compounds within the formulation. In contrast, a smaller or nonexistent zone means that there is a limited antimicrobial effect. This method offers simple and reproducible visual insulation about how well the formulated products work against different pathogens.

Treatment of Data

The results of experiments were compiled in the form of mean and standard deviation to define the antimicrobial activity of *Acalypha indica* ethanolic extract and its designed products. An interpretation system, descriptive and interpretative, was adapted to measure the zones of inhibition (ZOI, in millimeters), in conjunction with the values of Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC). Three reference tables were used in order to have a standardized structure towards which the appraisal is done.

The general classification of the microorganism inhibitory activity based on the values of MIC and MBC is described in Table 1, which makes it possible to characterize the extract's capability to prevent or kill microorganisms. Table 2 contains a method of antimicrobial efficacy scoring, which gives a scale of rating of the ideal level of antimicrobial response that is weak, moderate, strong, and very strong. Lastly, Table 3 presents the Guevarra Zone Diameter Interpretative Standard that provides clear standards of interpretation of ZOI with reference to levels of inhibition. These tools of interpretation provided a standard, analysis of all trials and formulations, allowed comparison of test organisms and levels.

Table 1.

Interpretation of Antimicrobial Activity Based on MIC and MBC Values

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Well Number	Growth (MIC)	Growth on Agar Plate (MBC)	Interpretation
1000	1	No Growth	No Colonies	Bactericidal
500	2	No Growth	Colonies Present	Bacteriostatic
250	3	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective
125	4	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective
62.5	5	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective
31.25	6	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective
15.625	7	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective
7.8125	8	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective

Ethical Consideration

The study was submitted for ethics review to Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) with address and contact information at 2nd Floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos; Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines (email: reb@smu.edu.ph; cellphone: 09177053041). The reference number is SMUREB code 2025 0851.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Section 1. Percentage Yield

Table 4 presents the percent yield of dried extract obtained from *Acalypha indica* after undergoing percolation. The mass of the dried plant material was weighed before extraction, and the weight of the resulting dried extract was recorded.

Table 4Percent yield of *A. indica* Extract

Solvent	Weight of dry extract (g)	Weight of dry plant material (g)	Percent yield (%)
Ethanol	43.40	100	43.40

From the data presented in Table 4, it was found that the ethanol extract of *A. indica* was 43.40%. This yield suggests a potential role of ethanol as an effective solvent for phytochemical extraction. This relatively high yield is attributed to the syrupy consistency of the extract, which retained excess solvent and residual moisture. Since the extract was not fully dried during concentration, it likely contained impurities and unremoved solvent, contributing to the high recovery percentage. Ethanol readily crosses cell membranes and can dissolve both polar and non-polar substances, so it is an excellent solvent for extracting bioactive compounds such as flavonoids, tannins, alkaloids, and saponins.

It has been observed in the aforementioned literature that high extract yield can be a consequence of the great abundance of phytochemicals, incomplete solvent evaporation, and the presence of non-bioactive compounds. In addition to extracting a wide range of polar and non-polar compounds, chlorophyll, sugars, and moisture-retaining constituents inflating the apparent mass of the extract, ethanol is considered an effective solvent (Harborne, 1998). The resulting broad solubility might yield additional substances that are not directly antimicrobial in the final yield. Tiwari et al. (2011) also pointed out that, if not adequately dried and further purified, extraction yields may be overestimated because of residues of glycerides, water-soluble matter, and even trace amounts of the extract solvent themselves. These results thus emphasize the necessity of post-extraction refinement steps to allow for a more accurate assessment of biologically active components.

Overall, the high extract yield in this study is due to both the broad ethanol solubility range and the retention of moisture and inactive compounds in the crude extract. This result may not be accurate with regards to the concentration of pharmacologically active constituents, whilst this result is advantageous for volume or quantity as it concerns formulation purposes. As a result, it is suggested that further studies use additional purification, drying, or fractionation steps in order to isolate and quantify the true bioactive compounds more precisely. Such measures would improve the accuracy of antimicrobial efficacy evaluation and improve the consistency of future product formulations.

Section 2. Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentrations (MBC)

Table 5 presents the Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) values of *A. indica*'s crude extract against the selected pathogens.

Table 5

Minimum Inhibitory Concentrations (MIC) and Minimum Bactericidal Concentrations (MBC) values

Microorganism	Plant Extract	Concentration (ug/ml)	MIC	MBC	Interpretation
<i>S. aureus</i>	Ethanol	250	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>		15.6	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective
<i>B. subtilis</i>		31.3	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective
<i>C. albicans</i>		31.3	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective
<i>E. coli</i>		250	Growth	Not Applicable	Ineffective
<i>E. faecalis</i>		500	No Growth	Colonies Present	Bacteriostatic

P. aeruginosa was the most susceptible, *Pseudomonas* was isolated to *Acalypha indica* extract by MIC values result and was found to have the lowest MIC value of 15.6 µg/mL. Given, in particular, that the pathogen is known to be multidrug-resistant and to have intrinsic defense mechanisms, this is especially significant. The ultimate MBC results indicated that the extract was able to cause bactericidal activity at comparably low concentrations in accordance with *E. faecalis* lethality. Moreover, *E. faecalis* had the highest value of MIC at 500 µg/mL, which indicated reduced susceptibility. Variation in antimicrobial response is likely a function of different cell wall composition, well-described efflux pump systems, and the organism's capacity to make biofilms that sequester antimicrobial agents from the killing surface.

In particular, phytochemicals like flavonoids, tannins, and alkaloids with an antimicrobial action have been shown to have mechanisms that interfere with the formation of nucleic acid, deactivation of enzymes, and disruption of the microbiological membranes (Cushnie et al. 2011). These compounds can affect such things as structural integrity and impair such events as essential cellular processes. For instance, Ríos et al. (2005) also mentioned that Gram-negative bacteria generally are more resistant due to an outer membrane but can be susceptible to phytochemicals that are able to penetrate or destabilize the barrier. Achieving these insights aids in understanding the extract's bactericidal and bacteriostatic capabilities against *P. aeruginosa* and *B. subtilis*. It supports the hypothesis that *A. indica* includes such agents that can breach many forms of microbial defense structures.

The MIC and MBC findings overall validate the antimicrobial efficacy of *A. indica* extract against drug-resistant and opportunistic pathogens. The extract displayed inhibition of the growth of bacteria at low concentrations in addition to its bactericidal effects, which is necessary for the complete elimination of pathogens. These results also suggest that *A. indica* has potential as a plant material for developing plant-based sanitizing products. This broad-spectrum activity offers practical use in the area of household disinfection and personal hygiene, particularly for those looking for alternatives that are natural and as low-cost alternatives to synthetic antimicrobials.

Section 3. Antimicrobial Potential of Formulated Products

Figure 4 illustrates the antimicrobial spray and liquid soap formulated with *A. indica*'s crude extract. These products were developed to assess their inhibitory effects against selected test microorganisms, showcasing the plant's potential as an antimicrobial agent.

Figure 4

Antimicrobial Spray & Liquid Soap (Front) Antimicrobial Spray & Liquid Soap (Back)

Table 6 show the antimicrobial potential of the formulated sanitizing spray and liquid soap, as measured by the diameter of the zones of inhibition against selected test microorganisms.

Table 6
Zone Inhibition of Test Substances – Spray & Liquid Soap

		ZOI (mm)		Mean ± SD	Interpretation	Percent (%)
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>						
Soap	Formulated	18.9	17	17.78±0.65	Strong	79.24
	Smart (+)	23.8	21.1	22.44±0.93	Very Strong	100
	Soap base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
Spray	Formulated	21.7	10.1	16.58±4.14	Moderate	92.84
	Lysol (+)	29.5	12.2	18.00±6.07	Very Strong	100
	Spray base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
<i>P. aeruginosa</i>						
Soap	Formulated	12	6.3	8.28 ± 2.04	Moderate to Weak	96.28
	Smart (+)	12.3	6.7	8.60 ± 1.94	Moderate	100
	Soap base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
Spray	Formulated	10.6	6.3	8.34 ± 1.64	Moderate	90.47
	Lysol (+)	11.4	6.4	9.22 ± 1.76	Moderate	100
	Spray base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
<i>B. subtilis</i>						
Soap	Formulated	16.2	11.5	13.50±1.63	Moderate	50.31
	Smart (+)	28.7	24.6	26.82±1.61	Strong	100
	Soap base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
Spray	Formulated	20.89	13.34	18.38±2.73	Strong	104.32
	Lysol (+)	24.62	15.29	17.62±3.61	Very Strong	100
	Spray base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
<i>C. albicans</i>						
Soap	Formulated	21.6	10.5	16.88±3.87	Strong	74.69
	Smart (+)	23.6	21	22.60±0.93	Very Strong	100
	Soap base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
Spray	Formulated	24.73	8.96	18.45±5.38	Very Strong	129.99
	Lysol (+)	30.4	0	14.19±9.99	Variable	100
	Spray base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
<i>E. coli</i>						
Soap	Formulated	7.8	0	1.56 ± 3.12	Weak	84.78
	Smart (+)	9.2	0	1.84 ± 3.68	Weak	100
	Soap base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
Spray	Formulated	11.27	6.95	8.39 ± 1.57	Moderate	86.12
	Lysol (+)	11.33	7.02	9.74 ± 1.5	Moderate	100
	Spray base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
<i>E. faecalis</i>						
Soap	Formulated	19.8	16.6	18.12±1.09	Strong	67.42
	Smart (+)	28.6	25.6	26.88±1.07	Very Strong	100
	Soap base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0
Spray	Formulated	19.4	15.4	17.26±1.63	Strong	98.52
	Lysol (+)	25.6	14.1	17.52±4.35	Variable	100
	Spray base (-)	0	0	0	No Activity	0

Note: Qualitative Interpretation: 0 mm = No Activity; 1–10 mm = Weak; 11–15 mm = Moderate; 16–20 mm = Strong;

Six specific pathogens were used to test the antimicrobial properties of the liquid soap and broad-spectrum sanitizing spray prepared from *Acalypha indica* (Bugos). Both formulations demonstrated evident zones of inhibition against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Candida albicans*, and *Enterococcus faecalis*, suggesting potent antimicrobial efficacy. The sizes of the inhibition zones noted for these microorganisms were significantly greater than those of the negative control, highlighting the formulations' ability to restrict microbial growth effectively. The products exhibited moderate activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Escherichia coli*, yielding measurable yet relatively smaller inhibition zones. Although they did not consistently surpass the effects of the commercial positive control (Smart), the findings still underscore the antimicrobial potential of the *A. indica*-based formulations. The results indicate that these plant-based products are effective against various Gram-positive bacteria, specific Gram-negative bacteria, and yeast, reinforcing their potential application as natural antimicrobial agents.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

This research study aimed to determine the antimicrobial potential of the different crude extracts of *Acalypha indica* (Bugos) and its formulated broad-spectrum sanitizing spray and liquid soap. The result shows that the ethanolic extract yielded 43.40 %, which suggests that it may contain a large concentration of bioactive components. The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) tests identified that the extract has high antimicrobial activity, which means that it can inhibit pathogens up to low concentrations. The Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) tests identified that the extract has low antimicrobial activity, meaning it cannot kill pathogens. Even if the MBC was low, a sanitizing spray and liquid soap were formulated. The zone of inhibition of the formulations shows strong, moderate, and weak, hence it can also be that the formulations may be suitable for basic household use, but they are not yet as effective as commercial disinfectants. Further studies are needed to enhance the extract's potency, isolate its active compounds, and improve the formulation.

Recommendations

1. Perform analyses and stability tests over time for verification of the blistered liquid soap and spray's safety, long life, and consumer interest.
2. Safety testing, including skin irritation assessments and allergen screenings, should be performed to validate the product's suitability for daily household use.
3. Stability testing should be conducted to determine the shelf life of products, using accelerated and real-time studies under various temperature and humidity conditions to ensure long-term safety, efficacy, and proper expiration labeling.

References

- Ahmad, I., Mehmood, Z., & Mohammad, F. (1998). Screening of some Indian medicinal plants for their antimicrobial properties. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9741890/>.
- Almeida, R., Sousa, L., Freitas, S., & Mendes, S. (2022). Development and optimization of *Clinacanthus nutans* liquid spray: A topical herbal formulation. *Pharmazie*, 77(2), 74-80.
<https://www.ingentaconnect.com/contentone/govi/pharmaz/2022/00000077/f0020003/art00004>
- Arulraj, S., & Sivakumar, T. (2017). Antimicrobial activity of *Acalypha indica* (L.) extracts in different solvents. *World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research*, 3(11), 61-65.
Retrieved from https://www.wjpmr.com/a-dmin/assets/article_issue/29112017/1511955817.pdf
- Azwanida, N. N. (2015). A review on the extraction methods use in medicinal plants, principle, strength and limitation. *Medicinal and Aromatic Plants*.
<https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?referenceid=2501890>
- Chopra, I., & Roberts, M. (2001). Tetracycline antibiotics: Mode of action, applications, molecular biology, and epidemiology of bacterial resistance. *Microbiology and Molecular Biology Reviews*.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/11381101/>.

- Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute. (2015). Methods for dilution antimicrobial susceptibility tests for bacteria that grow aerobically; approved standard (10th ed.). CLSI Document M07-A10.
- Cowan, M. M. (1999). Plant products as antimicrobial agents. National Library of Medicine, *PubMed Central*. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC88925/>
- Cushnie, T. P. T., & Lamb, A. J. (2011). Antibacterial properties of flavonoids. *International Journal of Antimicrobial Agents*. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/21514796/>.
- Eloff JN. (1998). A sensitive and quick microplate method to determine the minimal inhibitory concentration of
- Guevarra, B.Q. (2005). A guidebook to plant screening: Phytochemical and biological. *UST Publishing House*.
- Gupta, R., Khare, P., Lodhi, S., & Singh, M. (2013). *Phytochemical properties of Acalypha indica* (L.) and its antimicrobial potential against human pathogens. *Journal of Pure and Applied Microbiology*, 7(2), 987-993. <https://microbiologyjournal.org/phytochemical-properties-of-acalyphindica-land-its-antimicrobial-potential-against-human-pathogens/>
- Handa, S. S., Khanuja, S. P. S., Longo, G., & Rakesh, D. D. (2008). Extraction technologies for medicinal and aromatic plants. *International Development Research Centre*.
- Harborne, J. B. (1998). *Phytochemical methods: A guide to modern techniques of plant analysis*. Springer
- Iqbal, M., Sadiq, A., & Saeed, M. (2013). Antimicrobial activity of various extracts of medicinal plants against the multi-drug resistant bacteria. *Pakistan Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 26(4), 685-691.
- Kumar, K., Kumar, P., Pandey, S., & Raj, S. (2023). Efficacy of various extracting solvents on phytochemical composition and antioxidant potential of plant extracts. *Scientific Reports*, 13, 45030. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41598-023-45030-5>
- Ndhlala, A. R., Moyo, M., & Van Staden, J. (2013). The role of medicinal plants in the management of diabetes. In *Natural Products and Drug Development* (pp. 139161).
- Olowokudejo, J. D., Egunyomi, A., & Adebisi, A. (2008). An ethnobotanical survey of herbal markets and medicinal plants in Lagos State of Nigeria. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary, and Alternative Medicines*, 5(1), 31-38 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/41115540_An_Ethnobotanical_Survey_of_Herbal_Markets_and_Medicinal_Plants_in_Lagos_State_of_Nigeria
- Pandey & Tripathi, 2014 Pandey, A., & Tripathi, R. (2014). An overview of the potential of medicinal plants. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 8(12), 582-590.
- Pharmaceutical Research Journal. (2021). A review on secondary metabolites and pharmacology applications of *Acalypha indica* Linn. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research and Development*, 5(1), 48-52. <https://www.pharmaceuticaljournal.net/archives/2024/vol6issue2/PartA/6-2-10814.pdf>
- Rahman, A., Hossain, M., & Das, S. (2009). Phytochemical screening and antibacterial activity of some medicinal plants. *Research Journal of Medicinal Plant*, 3(2), 47-56.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262545720_Biological_properties_of_medicinal_plants_A_review_of_their_antimicrobial_activity.

Rios, J.L. & Recio M.C. (2005). Medicinal plants and antimicrobial activity. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*. *Science Direct*.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0378874105003247>.

Siddiqui, M. F., Shamsi, S. F., & Abbas, Q. (2015). Antibacterial activity of some medicinal plants against multidrug-resistant bacteria. *African Journal of Traditional, Complementary, and Alternative Medicines*, 12(2), 124-132
<https://www.ajol.info/index.php/ajtcam/article/view/120124>.

Tiwari, P., Kumar, D., Shukla, S., & Yadav, S. (2019). Formulation of liquid soap ethanol extract from Batak onion as an antifungal for *Candida albicans*. In *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Health and Medical Sciences* (pp. 43-48). *SciTePress*.
<https://www.scitepress.org/Papers/2019/98399/98399.pdf>

Tiwari, P., Kumar, B., Kaur, M., Kaur, G., & Kaur, H. (2011). Phytochemical screening and extraction: A review. *International Pharmaceutica Scientia*.
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Chukwuebuka-Egbuna/post/Whydoespetroleum-ether-solvent-yield-more-alkaloids-and-polyphenols-andwhy-doesaqueous-extraction-yield-moreflavonoids/attachment/59d650a779197b80779a968f/AS%3A504112410497024%401497201172241/download/Phytochemical+screening+and+extraction++A+review.pdf>